

external dressing was applied. The operation was one hour and fifteen minutes in length. The patient was in good condition at its close. A five-drachm rectal enema of peptonized milk containing five grains of bromide of sodium was given every four hours. Nothing was allowed by the mouth until the end of forty-five hours, at which time teaspoonful doses of boiled water were administered, followed a day later by teaspoonful doses of peptonized milk. During these first two days the child was exceedingly restless, sleeping at short intervals and constantly crying for water, but being relieved somewhat by frequent sponge baths. The pulse averaged 130 per minute, the temperature ranged from 100° to 101°; as soon as fluids could be administered by the mouth the little patient became more quiet and the pulse and temperature gradually fell. The first dressing was changed at the end of three days and the wound found to be aseptic; the rent in the esophagus could be seen at the bottom; there was no leakage. The dressing was changed under chloroform daily thereafter, packing being carried well to the bottom; this alternated between weak solutions of bichloride of mercury, carbolic acid and iodoform gauze, in order to avoid the possibility of drug poisoning. The wound gradually filled; there was at no time leakage from the esophagus, the sutures of sterile black silk were buried in the aseptic healing process, and fourteen days after the operation the little fellow was taken back to his home in Manitou. A recent letter from Dr. Ogilbee assures me that he has had no difficulty in swallowing; it is now a year since the operation. During the first few weeks after removal of the foreign body the voice was of high pitch and strident, but it has since resumed its normal tone.

But little need be said in way of comment on the class of accidents exemplified by the foregoing cases. In diagnosis we now have the invaluable assistance of the Röntgen ray; there can be no department of surgery in which this wonderful discovery finds better employment. Certainly it is to be resorted to in every instance in which we suspect the lodgment of a foreign body in the esophagus. In the first of the foregoing cases the picture was of no aid, but the skiagraph was not of the best and the nature and position of the foreign body was such as to render diagnosis even by the best possible picture exceedingly difficult. In the second case fluorescopic examination of the patient made accurate diagnosis absolutely certain; most startling and vivid was the clear and distinct picture of the iron wheel, plainly outlined in its definite relation to the bony thorax.

Management of these foreign bodies impacted in the esophagus must rest, when possible, on extraction through the mouth or on forcing them downward into the stomach; but we are not to forget that efforts at extraction may be in themselves dangerous, as when the sharp corners of a tooth-plate or a piece of bone may be driven into and through the wall of the esophagus; we are to remember the important point laid down by Richardson, of Boston, that the coin-catcher or throat instrument employed in attempting extraction may itself become impacted and necessitate immediate operation for its removal. It is well, therefore, before attempting extraction by instrumentation to have everything in readiness for the immediate performance of external esophagotomy should this be necessary. As one recalls the longitudinal position

which the wheel occupied in the little child's gullet, it seems quite possible that a coin-catcher passed below it and drawn upward might so tilt the foreign body as to impact it firmly against the spine or trachea or larynx and so render the instrument itself impossible of withdrawal. Further, we are not to forget that attempts at forcing downward a cervical foreign body may lodge it midway in the thoracic portion of the esophagus, where it would be difficult of access, either by esophagotomy or gastrotomy.

Of the operation itself but little need be said. The incision is the classic one; the various structures are plainly recognized step by step, and the important vessels and nerves carefully protected. After extraction of the foreign body the esophageal wall may be sutured, preferably by tiers of fine black silk, if the wall itself be in good condition; if it be ulcerated, the ulcer may be excised and the wall sutured, or the wound may be left open. The subject has been carefully considered in a recent and extended study by Bull and Walker. Whatever be the management of the wound in the esophagus, the external wound should not be sutured but should be carefully packed to the bottom; this wound may extend to or into the chest, and adequate packing is the best protection against sepsis. If the wound in the esophagus be left open, a stomach tube may be introduced through it at the time of operation, if the surgeon so desires. If the wound in the esophagus be closed primarily, it will be best to withhold everything by the mouth until such time as firm union is probable; distressing thirst may be much relieved by rectal injections and by frequent bathing. Should the stitches in the esophageal wall give way, it will be necessary to pack thoroughly until the hole is closed.

The mortality of the procedure will naturally vary with the different cases. It is most important not to delay operation until malnutrition saps the patient's strength. Further, the sharp corner of a foreign body may speedily ulcerate into and through the esophageal wall. Bull and Walker found the death-rate to be 22.5 per cent. in a total of 167 collected cases, though in the 32 most recent cases the mortality was diminished to 15.6 per cent. The earlier the operation is performed and the less the integrity of the esophageal wall is impaired the better will be the prognosis.

THE AMERICAN PEDIATRIC SOCIETY'S COLLECTIVE INVESTIGATION ON INFANTILE SCURVY IN NORTH AMERICA.¹

J. P. CROZER GRIFFITH, M.D., CHARLES G. JENNINGS, M.D.,
JOHN LOVETT MORSE, M.D., COMMITTEE.

(Concluded from Vol. cxxxviii, No. 26, p. 609.)

DIAGNOSIS.—The study of diagnosis has been only incidental, based upon the mistakes made before the disease was recognized in certain cases. The only disease for which infantile scurvy was repeatedly taken appears to have been rheumatism. In several instances the affection of the legs was supposed to be due to sarcoma. The apparent paralytic condition has also been the cause of error in some instances.

DURATION OF ILLNESS AND PROGNOSIS.—The disease is essentially chronic; its course terminating only on the institution of proper treatment. This seems to be proved by the answers contained in the cir-

¹ Reported at the Tenth Annual Meeting, Cincinnati, June 2, 1895.

culars. To the question concerning the *duration of the disease before the case came under observation*, replies were received in 306 cases, of which the following analysis may be made :

DURATION OF DISEASE BEFORE TREATMENT WAS COMMENCED.

Days.	Cases.	Weeks.	Cases.	Months.	Cases.
2	3	1	15	1	18
3	3	2	33	2	42
5	2	3	58	3	31
8	1	4	22	4	14
9	1	5	8	5	4
10	9	6	29	6	7
24	1	7	6	7	2
		8	1	10	1
		10	3	12	1
				2½ yrs.	1

Intensely interesting in this connection are the replies to the next two questions : first, *Duration of illness after treatment was commenced*; and, second, *Duration of treatment before marked improvement was noticed*. To the first question replies concerning 308 cases were received. Of course those fatal during the attack of scurvy are not included here nor those which passed from observation.

Still more striking are the answers to the second question, as to the time when marked improvement was first noticed. There are 311 cases suitable for study in this category, excluding fatal cases and those passing from observation as before. The replies are often astonishing. Nothing is more striking than the speed with which these reports show a grave constitutional disease disappearing under proper treatment. There is certainly no disease for which a more specific treatment can be said to exist. The replies to the last two questions may be conveniently stated in the following tables :

DURATION OF TREATMENT BEFORE MARKED IMPROVEMENT WAS NOTICED.

Days.	Cases.	Weeks.	Cases.	Months.	Cases.
1	19	1	47	1	6
2	58	2	27	2	4
3	46	3	8	3	4
4	26	4	1		
5	19	5	1		
6	1	6	1		
7	2				
8	2				
9	1				
10	7				
12	2				

Reported as prompt recovery, 13; at once, 15; immediate, 1.

DURATION OF TREATMENT BEFORE RECOVERY WAS COMPLETE.

Days.	Cases.	Weeks.	Cases.	Months.	Cases.
1	6	1	48	1	28
2	5	2	54	2	14
3	14	3	36	3	5
4	8	4	14	4	2
5	5	5	6	5	1
6	1	6	14	6	2
8	2	7	1	7	1
10	17			8	1
12	3			9	1
13	3				
15	2				
16	1				

Reported as immediate, 4; almost immediate, 9.

TREATMENT. — Not so much could be learned of the value of treatment as could be desired on account of the fact that in nearly all cases we have a combination of diet and of medicinal measures, including the use of fruit juices, and it is impossible to determine absolutely which was the active curative agent.

Taking the cases in which treatment was effectual and which are suitable for study, the results may be stated as follows :

I. Cases recovering under treatment with drugs only (no change in diet)	0
II. Cases recovering under the use of fruit juice alone (no change in diet)	3
III. Cases recovering under the use of beef juice alone (no other change in diet)	2
IV. Cases recovering under the use of beef juice and fruit juice combined, with or without drugs (no change in diet)	6
V. Cases recovering under the combined effect of change of diet, often including beef juice, and employment of fruit juice, with or without drugs	257
VI. Cases recovering under change of diet, often including beef juice, and use of drugs (no fruit juice)	20
VII. Cases recovering under change of diet alone, often including beef juice (no fruit juice)	38

These last two may be properly considered together, since there is no evidence that any treatment with drugs has an appreciable effect upon the disease. So many of the reported cases were treated with drugs alone without result before the correct diagnosis was made and other treatment instituted, that this belief is amply justified. Combining, therefore, Divisions VI and VII, and comparing the statements of the writers regarding the diet employed during treatment and that employed when the scurvy developed, we may make the following table based upon 58 cases.

Again the committee would state that no claim is made that the recovery was the result of the change, but that it quotes merely the statements of the correspondents to the effect that recovery took place after the change was made.

VI AND VII. — RECOVERY FOLLOWING CHANGE IN DIET ALONE, WITH OR WITHOUT DRUGS. (NO FRUIT JUICE EMPLOYED.)

Mellin's food to milk and beef juice	2
" " to raw milk and beef juice	1
" " to modified milk	4
" " to modified milk and beef juice	2
" " to diet and beef juice	1
" " and sterilized milk to beef juice and broths	1
" " and sterilized milk to sterilized milk and beef juice	2
" " and condensed milk to modified milk	1
" " and condensed milk to raw milk	2
" " and sarcopепtone to fresh milk and beef juice	1
Condensed milk to fresh milk and beef juice	1
" " to sterilized milk and diet	1
" " to lactated food and raw milk	1
" " to sterilized milk	1
Malted milk to milk and diet	1
" " to raw milk and beef juice	1
" " and amylaceæ to modified Pasteurized milk and beef juice	1
Sterilized milk to diet and beef juice	1
" " to fresh milk and beef juice	2
" " to raw milk	4
" " to diet	6
" " to raw milk and beef juice	1
" " to sterilized milk and beef juice	1
" " peptonized to raw milk and beef juice	1
" " to Pasteurized milk and diet	1
" " to Pasteurized milk	1
Pasteurized milk to raw milk	2
" " to fresh milk and beef juice	1
" " to sterilized milk and broths	1
Raw milk to amylaceæ	1
Breast milk to peptonized milk and broths	1
" " to sterilized milk	1
Lactated food to raw milk and beef juice	1
Reed & Carnrick's soluble food to modified milk	1
" " to baked potato	1
" " to beef juice	1
Imperial granum to raw milk and beef juice	1
Patented food to diet	1
Ridge's food to diet	1
Diet (poor) to diet (better)	2
Bartlett's pepsinated food to fresh milk	1

It must be noted with regard to this table and those following that the term "modified" milk is used very loosely by the reporters. Occasionally it is specified to be laboratory milk, but much oftener this is not the case, and we are unable to know whether the modification was done at home or not, and whether the milk was heated or not. Presumably it was Pasteurized in many instances. Where the term "fresh" milk is employed in the table, we have been unable to learn by additional correspondence whether "raw" milk is meant or whether only a change from proprietary food to cow's milk is intended. The term "diet" as em-

ployed in the tables either expresses the fact that a large and varied number of different forms of diet were tried, too complicated to be detailed, or else quotes merely the statement of the writers that a change of diet was made, the original food probably being abandoned entirely unless otherwise stated.

The following table shows the food employed in Divisions I, II, III and IV, in which the diet was the same (except sometimes for the addition of beef juice) while the scurvy was developing and while it was recovering.

RECOVERY FOLLOWING WITH NO CHANGE OF DIET DURING TREATMENT.

I. Treatment with drugs only	0
II. Treatment with fruit juice only	3
Mellin's food (milk sterilized)	1
Sterilized milk	2
III. Treatment with beef juice only	2
Sterilized milk	1
Raw milk	1
IV. Treatment with combined beef juice and fruit juice only,	6
Sterilized milk	2
Sterilized milk and broths	2
Sterilized milk and amylaceæ	1
Table food	1

Division V contains by far the largest number of cases, 257 in all. The changes in diet employed are much too complicated to be stated fully in the table. Moreover, they are of little value, since the treatment was such a composite one, namely, change of diet combined with the use of fruit juice in every case, and often of beef juice and of drugs as well. A few of the more striking classes of cases may be selected as follows:

V.—RECOVERY FOLLOWING CHANGE OF DIET COMBINED WITH FRUIT JUICE, WITH OR WITHOUT DRUGS.

Condensed milk to milk, variously treated	23
Imperial granum to milk, variously treated	7
Lactopreparata to raw milk	2
Lactated food to milk	3
Reed & Carnrick's Soluble Food to milk, variously treated	1
Malted milk to milk, variously treated	38
Mellin's food to milk, variously treated	21
Mellin's food and condensed milk to milk, variously treated	19
Sterilized milk to fresh (probably always raw) milk	34
Sterilized milk to Pasteurized milk	4
Pasteurized milk to "fresh" or "raw" milk	9
Pasteurized milk to sterilized milk	1
Raw milk to sterilized milk	1
Breast milk to cow's milk, variously treated	6

The conclusions to be drawn from this combined study of etiology and of treatment seem justifiable only to the following extent:

(1) That the development of the disease follows in each case the prolonged employment of some diet unsuitable to the individual child, and that often a change of diet which at first thought would seem to be unsuitable may be followed by prompt recovery.

(2) That in spite of this fact regarding individual cases, the combined report of collected cases makes it probable that in these there were certain forms of diet which were particularly prone to be followed by the development of scurvy. First in point of numbers here are to be mentioned the various proprietary foods.

(3) In fine, that in general the cases reported seem to indicate that the farther a food is removed in character from the natural food of a child the more likely its use is to be followed by the development of scurvy.

FATAL CASES.—Twenty-nine of the 379 cases are reported to have died. In 2 of these, death seems to have been remote from the attack of scurvy. Of the remaining 27 the causes as enumerated by the reporters are as follows:

Exhaustion, 6; cerebral hemorrhage, 3; diarrhea, 2; bronchitis, 2; vomiting (?) 1; convulsions, 1; pneumonia,

4; malnutrition, 1; pulmonary hemorrhage, 1; ulcer of stomach, 1; syncope and nephritis, 1; doubtful, 4.

It is difficult to determine in how many of these the scurvy itself could be held responsible for the death; probably in few if any.

AUTOPSIES.—There have been handed in to the committee the reports of 6 autopsies in all, some of them only partial. The salient points of each may be enumerated as follows:

Case of Dr. A. Caillé. Child of nine months, ill about three months. Autopsy showed hemorrhagic spots on the pericardium and surface of the liver; sub-periosteal hemorrhage of the long bones.

Case of Dr. L. E. Holt. Child of twelve months; ill for two months. Autopsy showed separation of the lower epiphysis from the shaft of the left femur; extensive sub-periosteal hemorrhage of the left femur; sub-pleural hemorrhages; broncho-pneumonia.

Case of Dr. L. E. Holt. Child of thirteen months; ill about two months. Autopsy showed sub-periosteal hemorrhage and separation of the lower epiphysis of the left femur; hemorrhages into the muscles of the left thigh, swellings about the opposite knee and both ankles; knee-joints normal; minute sub-pleural hemorrhages; well-marked exudative nephritis; minute hemorrhages on the surface of the liver.

Case of W. P. Northrup. (The first autopsy in the United States.) Child of eighteen months; ill about one month. Autopsy showed sub-periosteal hemorrhage of both tibiae and both femora; detachment of the lower epiphysis of the left femur and maceration of lower end of shaft; broncho-pneumonia of left lung; no rachitic or syphilitic changes on microscopical examination.

Case of Dr. L. Starr. Child thirteen months; ill for three months. Autopsy showed "right leg from knee to ankle stuffed with a puffy mass replacing normal tissue. Separation of both bones one inch above ankle."

Case of Dr. C. W. Townsend. Child of ten months; ill three to four weeks. Autopsy showed bloody serum in pleural cavity; perforating ulcer of the stomach; tubercular (?) process in peritoneum.

In conclusion the committee would thank publicly their correspondents who have sent reports of cases and who are enumerated elsewhere. They are also much indebted to Dr. Wm. Schleif, of Philadelphia, for valuable aid in analyzing the circulars received and tabulating the results.

Clinical Department.

A CASE OF PAPILOMATOUS URETHRITIS.

BY F. G. BALCH, M.D., BOSTON.

TUMORS of the urethra are of comparatively infrequent occurrence or, at least, are rarely recognized. Papillomata, polypi and carcinomata occur, and I have found one case of keloid reported. Of these, papillomata are the most common. According to Klotz, they occur in or near the meatus frequently, but they are much less common farther down the urethra. Goldenburg thinks they are not rare, certainly not as rare as most authors are inclined to think, and will be found often, the more frequently the endoscopic method is used. The reported cases are not numerous, and, for my own part, I am inclined to consider them of rare occurrence. Papillomata are usually multiple, bleed easily and are sometimes tender.

Polypi are less common than papillomata. They

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